

TWO NEW NATICIDAE (MOLLUSCA, GASTROPODA) FROM ANGOLA

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Introduction

The family Naticidae FORBES, 1838 has been studied and revised by several authors. SOWERBY (1883), in particular, presents a general revision of it.

Other publications deal with species from more restricted areas as, for example, Vigo Bay (ROLÁN, 1983), Canary Islands (NORDSIECK & TALAVERA, 1979), Maroc (PASTEUR-HUMBERT, 1962), Gabon (BERNARD, 1985), Mediterranean waters (D'ANGELO & GARGIULLO, 1978; SABELLI & SPADA, 1980; VILLA, 1985, 1986) and European seas (NORDSIECK, 1968). For African coasts, mentions can be found in DAUTZENBERG (1910, 1913), NICKLES (1950), DIXON & RYALL (1985, 1986). From Angola there are the lists of PINTO *et al.* (1975) and GOFAS *et al.* (1985).

But we are still far from having a complete knowledge of this family for the African coasts and some new species were described in last years by SAUNDERS (1978) and FERNANDES & ROLAN (in press).

During the revision that the authors are doing of the family in Angolan waters, samples of two species were studied because they do not have characteristics similar to the previously known ones. Comparison of shell characters and also of those from the radula and operculum led to the conclusion that both represented new species and they are described in the present work.

Taxonomic part.

Family *Naticidae* FORBES, 1838

Genus *Natica* SCOPOLI, 1777

Natica ryalli sp. nov.

Plate I, figs. 1-6

Description: Shell of very small size for the genus, with a medium length of 5-7 mm in type material. The biggest specimen has 8,2 mm in maximum length. Five to six convex spiral whorls of an oval shape, low spire and straightly marked suture,

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straight columella and a sharp semicircular lip. Umbilicum open with a barely visible funicule, where growth striae are visible. Shell coloration of a creambrownish to fulvous, sometimes cream-white to white, with a subsutural thin darker band. This upper body colour is limited two thirds down, near base, by a cream white spiral band. Around the umbilicus is generally tinted of brown-reddish, sometimes like a band that begins on the parietal callous, goes around the umbilicus and finishes on the internal lip. External lip bordered on the outside by a thin white fillet; aperture is pure white, apex whitish and inside umbilicus cavity is generally cream-white. Periostracum light brown and thin.

Fig. 1 — Operculum and its medial section of *Natica ryalli* n. sp.

Operculum (text fig. 1) calcareous, white, thin, smooth and lightly concave, nuclear callous small and clear; outer margin bordered with one barely visible striation, columellar margin a little raised on parietal zone.

Radula taenioglossa (text fig. 3) with a rachidian tooth elongate and quadrate in shape, a thick base and with two small cusps on both sides. The lateral tooth has a hand-shape gently curved and a little broader on the middle area. Marginal teeth simple and gently curved.

Fig. 2 — Operculum and its medial section of *Natica dixoni* n. sp.

Material studied: Angola: 45 spp collected in -6 m, off Palmeirinhas Point, 60 km South of Luanda (leg. F. FERNANDES).

Ghana: 15 spp collected in 8-15 m deep in Mia-Mia Bay (leg. P. RYALL).

Type material: Holotype (plate I, fig. 1) with a length of 6,2 mm deposited in the Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales de Madrid. Paratypes: 2 in the following collections: Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris; British Museum (Natural History), London; American Museum, New York. 15 in the P. RYALL collection, Ghana. 10 in the E. ROLÁN collection, Vigo. 26 in the F. FERNANDES collection, Luanda.

Type locality: Palmeirinhas Point, 60 km South of Luanda, Angola.

Distribution: So far known only from Angola and Ghana, it is possible that the present species exists in intermediate places.

Etimology: It is dedicated to Peter RYALL, malacologist from Ghana, for his cooperation in the present work as well as in many other researches.

Discussion: *Natica ryalli* sp. nov. has been known for a long time, but it was considered as a colour form of *N. adansoni* BLAINVILLE, 1825. This last species, in juvenile stages, has a strong funicular callous, a more globous shell shape, darker apex and a blueish aperture marked by a white spiral band. Its operculum has two cords close the outer lip.

Lunatia fusca (BLAINVILLE, 1825) has a bigger shell with a more uniform colour and moreover the operculum is corneus.

Natica cruentata LAMARCK, 1822 in juvenile stages, when it does not have the dark spots or flammulae and the body whorl is covered by small fulvous dots and points, can be similar, but has a different body shape, wider aperture without the white fillet on the outside of the external lip and, on the inside, the external pattern can be seen by transparence; the parietal callus is more developed and the brown colour is present only in the aperture of the umbilicus. Also its operculum is bordered by two clearly visible deep furrows.

Natica vittata corimbensis (FERNANDES & ROLAN, in press) reaches in Angola the same size as the new species but it is a more globous shell with a transparent external lip showing by transparence the external pattern, tawny shade aperture and with a funicular callus which almost closes the umbilicus aperture. Its operculum has two cords close the outer bord.

Natica dixoni sp. nov.

Plate I, fig. 7-8

Description: Shell of a moderate small size for the genus (below 22 mm), globose, thick and solid, with a good gloss. Two nuclear whorls continued by three to four postnuclear whorls with a smooth surface, including below the sutures, except from normal axial growth striae. Spire a little elevate, approximately one third of total shell height. Spire whorls gently convexly rounded, distinctly flattened below sutures. These are strongly impressed. Aperture pyriformly ovate, more widely fla-

red at the anterior half, and gently concave along the columellar wall. Outer lip proportionately thin and brittle. Umbilicus confined to a very small area, circular and very deep, extending internally right up into the spire, largely overhung by a thin but extensive parietal callus, which descends obliquely, intercepting a point two thirds down the inner lip. Within the umbilicus is a narrow, sharply-angular funicular ridge which produces, at lower columellar wall, a tiny triangular callous pad (not always clearly evident in some specimens).

A distinctive colour pattern on the body whorl consists of discrete narrow spiral bands of solid dull yellowish-brown, alternating with rather broader spiral zones of cream white, densely overlaid by numerous reddish brown speckles and blotches, which are extremely variable in size and shape within each zone. This speckling is generally most prominent and dense around the shoulder. Another distinctive feature is a solid spiral band or bright orange brown running immediately below the suture; this, and the speckled banding, continue onto earlier whorls, with the protoconch becoming a uniform tan colour. A narrow clear zone of white, encircles the umbilical basal area. Parietal callus also white. Aperture interior white, with a median spiral band of dark brown deeper within.

Fig. 3 — Radular teeth of a sp. of 7,4 mm of *Natica ryalli* n. sp. (Scale bar 0,1 mm)

The operculum (text fig. 2) is calcareous, thin, noticeably concave, glossy white, bearing two closely adjacent spiral ribs, set some way from the outer margin. These ribs are thin, with gently convex tops and very low. Nuclear area clear, free from accretions, producing a slight comma-shaped riblet anteriorly. Posterior two thirds of inner margin minutely serrated, scarcely visible to the naked eye.

Fig. 4 — Radular teeth of a sp. of 15,2 mm of *Natica dixoni* n. sp. (Scale bar 0,1 mm)

Periostracum light brown, quite thick, semiopaque, distinctly wrinkled with numerous axial creases which are most noticeable around the periphery.

The living animal has a foot with a beautiful pale orange, punctuated by numerous paler, yellowish round maculations. Tentacles are a pale shade of peachy yellow.

Radula (text fig. 4) *taenioglossa*, with central tooth elongate, gently curved with one small cusp on both sides and on the opposite sides at basal zone. Lateral tooth has a comma-shape, gently curved and thinner on the external part. Marginal teeth gently curved, one regularly uniform and the proximal is angulated one third, near basal implantation.

Material studied: Angola: 2 shells and 4 spp at low tide, Baía das Pipas; 1 sp at low tide, Baía Azul; 4 spp at low tide, Baía do Cacucaco, Luanda; 4 shells and 10 spp at -20 m, and 2 shells and 6 spp at low tide, Baía da Corimba, Luanda; 2 spp at Praia Santiago; 2 shells and 6 spp at low tide, Praia Amélia; 2 spp in -3 mm, Ponta Piambo. All leg. F. FERNANDES.

Type material: Holotype with 20,8 mm deposited in the Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales de Madrid. One paratype in the following collections: Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris; British Museum (Natural History), London; American Museum of Natural History, New York. 4 in the P. RYALL collection, Ghana. 5 in the E. ROLÁN collection, Vigo. 20 in the F. FERNANDES collection, Luanda.

Type locality: Pipas Bay, South Angola, at 30 km from Namibe (ex Mossâmedes).

Distribution: Only known from Angolan coasts.

Etimology: It is dedicated to R. Michael DIXON, malacologist, who figured the present species for the first time.

Discussion: DIXON & RYALL (1985) showed a moon shell of the present species from Angola as *Natica* sp. cf. *Natica gruveli* and they said that it has a distinctive colour pattern but very close in general morphology to *Natica gruveli* DAUTZENBERG, 1910.

N. gruveli displays the discrete spiral banding so characteristic of *N. dixonii* sp. nov. and never has neither alternating solid and speckled zones nor the solid orange subsutural band. In opposition its subsutural area is nearly always streaky or blotched. The operculum of *N. gruveli* has one bigger spiral cord adjacent to the outer margin and it is marked by a central sulcus, instead of the two very fine cords of *N. dixonii*.

Both species are sympatric in Angolan coasts without intermediate forms.

RESUMEN

Se describen dos nuevas especies del género *Natica* SCOPOLI, 1777 procedentes de las costas de Angola, siendo comparadas con las especies del género con mayor semejanza.

ABSTRACT

Two new species of the genus *Natica* SCOPOLI, 1777 from Angola coast are described. The comparison with the most similar species in the genus is done.

Key words: Naticidae, Angola, West Africa.

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Fig. 1-6 — *Natica ryalli*.

Fig. 7-8 — *Natica dixoni*.

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